

STATE AND LAW

VIOLETION OF THE RIGHTS OF WESTERN AZERBAIJANIS AND THE POLICY OF ETHNIC CLEANSING AGAINST THEM

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Abstract

During the last two hundred years, as a result of complex political processes in the historical territory of Azerbaijan, Azerbaijanis have been victims of forced displacement from their ancestral homes, ethnic cleansing and deportation policy. As a result of this step-by-step inhumane policy, Azerbaijanis were expelled from the territory now called Armenia - from their native historical-ethnic land, where they lived for thousands of years, and were subjected to mass murders and massacres, and the historical and cultural heritage belonging to Azerbaijanis, including mosques and cemeteries, were massively destroyed. destroyed, place names were changed, systematic racial discrimination was carried out against our compatriots.

Keywords: deportation, ethnic cleansing, genocide, responsibility, discrimination, torture.

In XIX century, thanks to the support of the imperial forces, the process of repressing Azerbaijanis in their historical lands was started with the mass transfer of Armenians from other territories to Azerbaijan. As a result of the policy of ethnic cleansing and genocide carried out purposefully against Azerbaijanis since the beginning of XX century by Armenian nationalists in order to realize the mythical idea of "Great Armenia", our people have been subjected to severe deprivations, national tragedies and hardships.

Decision No. 4083 of the Council of Ministers of the USSR dated December 23, 1947 "On the transfer of collective farmers and other population from the Armenian SSR to the Kur-Araz lowland of the Azerbaijan SSR", the second decision No. 754 adopted in addition to this decision, dated March 10, 1948 "On measures related to the transfer of collective farmers and other Azerbaijani population from Armenian SSR to the Kur-Araz lowland of the Azerbaijan SSR" was the next historical criminal act against the people of Azerbaijan. Based on these decisions, about 150,000 Azerbaijanis were evicted from their places of residence and forcibly relocated from their native land. During the execution of these decisions, which are contrary to the norms of international law, the current rules of repression of the authoritarian-totalitarian regime were widely applied, and thousands of people, including the elderly and babies, died, not enduring the harsh conditions of displacement, drastic climate change, physical shocks and moral genocide.

Thus, as a result of the insidious policies and atrocities committed by the infamous Armenians in various periods of XX century, nearly two million of our compatriots were displaced from their historical homeland, hundreds of thousands of Azerbaijanis were

subjected to gross violations of human rights and freedoms, torture and inhumane treatment in violation of international law due to their nationality, genocide, ethnic cleansing policy and severe torture and were brutally murdered. At the same time, many cities and villages where they live have been turned into ruins.

After Azerbaijan regained its state independence, an opportunity arose to present an objective picture of the historical past of our nation, and truths that had been kept secret for many years and banned were revealed one by one.

It should be noted that only after the National Leader Heydar Aliyev returned to power in 1993 at the insistence of the people, the truth about the genocide, deportation and other crimes against humanity committed by Armenian nationalists was conveyed to the world community. Consistent, purposeful and decisive steps have been taken in the direction of giving them the correct political and legal value.

The correct value of the tragedy of our compatriots who lived in Western Azerbaijan was given for the first time by the National Leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev. On December 18, 1997, our great leader signed the Decree "On the mass deportation of Azerbaijanis from their historical and ethnic lands in the territory of the Armenian SSR in 1948-1953" on December 18, 1997, in order to comprehensively investigate the mass deportation of Azerbaijanis [1]. With this Decree, a legal and political value was given to this historical crime committed at the state level against the people of Azerbaijan and the reactionary nature of the policy of ethnic cleansing against Azerbaijanis was conveyed to the international community.

With the decree of the great leader Heydar Aliyev "On the Genocide of Azerbaijanis" dated March 26, 1998, giving a political and legal value to the acts of

genocide gave an impetus to the research conducted in this field and to increase the efforts towards uncovering the truth. In order to commemorate all the genocide tragedies committed against the Azerbaijani people, March 31 was declared "Azerbaijani Genocide Day" [2].

At the same time, the Great Leader's Decree "On solving the settlement problems of Azerbaijanis displaced from their historical lands in the territory of Armenia as a result of ethnic cleansing carried out by Armenian nationalists" dated August 22, 2001 was one of the important steps in terms of solving housing and other problems of our compatriots from Western Azerbaijan [3].

In addition, in the Order "On the 100th Anniversary of the Genocide of the Azerbaijanis of 1918" dated January 12, 2018, signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev, it is reflected that Armenian nationalists carried out ethnic cleansing, deportation and genocide against our compatriots at various stages of history and committed against Azerbaijanis, the implementation of appropriate measures was determined in order to more fully convey the truths about crimes against humanity to the country and the world community.

People who participated in ethnic cleansing and other crimes against Azerbaijanis in the territory called Armenia and their actions were glorified at the state level in Armenia.

This unprecedented injustice has created a sense of impunity in the ruling circles of Armenia and encouraged them to claim territory, use force, military occupation, additional mass-scale ethnic cleansing and other crimes against humanity against the internationally recognized territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan. People representing the political and military leadership of Armenia, inspired by the atmosphere of impunity, used the double standards applied in relation to Azerbaijan for their own ugly and insidious purposes, and committed crimes against peace and humanity, war and terrorism against Azerbaijanis.

Today, it should be noted with pride that the brave Azerbaijani Army under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Victorious Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, ended the 44-day Patriotic War with victory. He restored the territorial integrity of our country and the violated rights of Azerbaijanis who were displaced from their homelands for about 30 years. However, the inability of Azerbaijanis who were expelled from the territory of Armenia to return to their homes, the continuation of mono-ethnic statehood, ethnic cleansing and systematic racial discrimination in this country is a great injustice and poses a serious threat to the establishment of lasting peace.

It should be noted that the punishment of the Armenian state for the international crimes and inhumane treatment committed by the Armenians against the statehood and people of Azerbaijan, the restoration of the violated human rights and freedoms of our compatriots, and the payment of compensation can only be ensured by the norms and principles of international law. Because the Armenian state, which ignores the human

rights and freedoms established by important international norms, and the obligations for the implementation of these rights and freedoms, committed against the Azerbaijanis with the threat of intimidation, hatred, and cruel ethnic cleansing, massacres, torture, the destruction of historical and cultural monuments is not only a violation of general international legal norms, but also a gross and serious violation of fundamental human rights and freedoms established in international conventions.

In order to assess the deportation of our compatriots who lived in Western Azerbaijan from an international legal point of view, it is necessary to view Article 7 of the Statute of the International Criminal Court. Thus, according to Article 7.2 of the Statute, "deportation or forced relocation of the population" means the forced relocation of persons targeted for relocation or other compulsory measures from the territory of their legal residence without grounds permitted by international law [9]. The deportation and resettlement policy of Armenians against Azerbaijanis can be considered the "intersection point" of three types of violations of international law norms - violation of human rights, international humanitarian law norms, as well as the occurrence of crimes against humanity.

The prohibition of ethnic cleansing, as well as its interaction with the crime of genocide, is reflected in various documents accepted at the international legal level. Thus, in the Resolution of the UN General Assembly "On Ethnic Cleansing and Racial Hatred" dated December 16, 1992, ethnic cleansing was unconditionally condemned. Its incompatibility with universally recognized human rights and fundamental freedoms, the prosecution of the perpetrators of acts of ethnic cleansing and their transfer to justice and individual criminal responsibility, and the immediate cessation of any person who commits ethnic cleansing or orders such acts, the necessity of cooperation of the states in the field of cancellation of all forms of this act were emphasized [10].

Those provisions mentioned in the resolution can serve as a legal tool for the international legal recognition of the "ethnic cleansing" policy of Armenians against Azerbaijanis and the prosecution of the perpetrators of this crime.

The policy of ethnic cleansing and genocide of Armenians against Azerbaijanis is directly consistent with the tendency of forceful seizure of Azerbaijani lands. Because in relation to Azerbaijan and Azerbaijanis, the policy of ethnic cleansing→genocide→aggression are inseparable chain links that complement each other and are considered to be part of the same process.

The crimes committed by Armenia as a result of the policy of ethnic cleansing against Azerbaijanis are included in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, international covenants "On Civil and Political Rights", "On Economic, Social and Cultural Rights", "On the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms", "Prevention of the Crime of Genocide and on the Punishment", "On the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination", "On the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Apartheid", "Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or

Punishment", "The Violence of All Persons on protection from disappearances" contrary to the principles of human dignity, freedom and security, citizenship, equality before the law, not to be subjected to discrimination, torture, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, which is contrary to the principles of human dignity approved in conventions and other international documents is a violation of protection, education, labor, property, return and other fundamental rights without disappearance.

In order to eliminate these violations committed in the condition of impunity, to restore the rights of our victim compatriots, and most importantly, to achieve recognition of such crimes at the international level as one of the most important components of the return to West Azerbaijan, it is necessary to evaluate these acts from the point of view of international law.

According to Articles 5 and 7 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the first fundamental document in the field of human rights, all persons are equal before the law and have the right to equal protection against any discrimination and any attempt at such discrimination. No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

According to Articles 6 and 7 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, to which Armenia is also a party, the right to life, which is an inalienable right of every person, is protected by law. No one can be arbitrarily deprived of life. No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

Article 26 of the Covenant states that all persons are equal before the law and have the right to equal protection of the law without any discrimination. All forms of discrimination in this regard must be prohibited by law, and the law prohibits discrimination on the grounds of race, skin color, sex, language, religion, political or other beliefs, national or social affiliation, property status or other status must provide equal and effective protection to all persons.

One of the important requirements of the Covenant is that no state, group or individual may engage in any activity aimed at the unlawful restriction or destruction of human rights at the international level.

The mentioned international documents also mention the right to freedom and free movement and return. Thus, according to Article 13 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 12 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, everyone has the right to move freely within the borders of each state, to leave any country and to return to their own country. No one can be denied the right to come to his country [6].

As a result of the ethnic cleansing, genocide and other crimes against humanity committed by the occupying Armenia against the Azerbaijanis, as mentioned in the international documents, the right to live, equality before the law, free movement, return, discrimination, torture or inhuman and degrading treatment or punishment non-exposure and other fundamental human rights and freedoms have been grossly and seriously violated, but no international legal accountability

measures have been applied to date. Because for many years, our hated enemies prevented the real truth from being conveyed to the international community and prevented the resolution of the conflict in accordance with the principles of international law. It is this feature that has created conditions for the Armenian state to be exempt from responsibility for the violations it has committed.

Armenia, which is a party to the European Convention "On the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms" and the Protocols attached to it, committed international crimes against our compatriots and the international crimes reflected in these legal documents and universally accepted rights to life, freedom of movement, protection of property, forced removal of citizens, separate -deliberately and grossly violated norms and principles such as the prohibition of discrimination and torture [7].

Regarding the international legal analysis of the genocide crimes committed by Armenia against our people, first of all, it is important to look at the provisions of the 1948 Convention "On the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide" [8].

Thus, according to that document, genocide, prohibited by international law, is the killing of members of a group, serious physical injuries or serious damage to mental capacity, for the purpose of the partial or total destruction of any national, ethnic, racial or religious group, intentional killing of any group, is the creation of living conditions that involves complete or partial physical destruction, the implementation of measures aimed at preventing birth within the group, and the forced transfer of children belonging to the group to another group. According to Articles 1 and 4 of the Convention, the Contracting Parties affirm that genocide is a crime that violates the norms of international law, regardless of whether it is committed during peace or war, and undertake to prevent and punish this crime, and commit any of these acts a person should be punished regardless of whether he is a constitutionally responsible leader, official or individual.

Although the crimes of genocide committed by Armenians against our people with unprecedented brutality are a serious violation of the Convention "On the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide" and international humanitarian law norms, no punitive measures have been implemented at the international level against those who committed these acts.

At the same time, the international crimes committed by Armenia against the state and people of Azerbaijan are considered jus cogens norms of international law, in the UN Charter, in the UN General Assembly Declaration No. territorial integrity, inviolability of borders, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, non-use of force or threat of use of force, peaceful settlement of international disputes, conscientious fulfillment of international obligations as stipulated in the Helsinki Final Act of the Council on Security and Cooperation in Europe (CSCE) and other basic principles are considered to be a serious, gross and systematic violation, Armenia must answer for those actions before the international mechanisms.

As a subject of international law, Azerbaijan also recognizes the obligation to comply with the main principles of international law, and has the right to demand from the world states the duty to respect these guiding principles. The most important of the factors that make this necessary is the clear violation by Armenia of the existing principles in relation to Azerbaijan.

Of course, in accordance with Article 51 of the UN Charter, despite the existence of Azerbaijan's right to self-defense, our state, once again showing its commitment to the generally recognized principles and norms of international law, always maintains a peaceful and non-war policy, and offers all possible compromise options for the sake of peace in the world and the region [4]. And Armenia does not give up its policy of aggression and still continuing international crimes, veiled by double standards.

Thus, the forced relocation of Western Azerbaijanis from their native historical-ethnic lands, where they live, is a serious and systematic violation of numerous fundamental human rights principles, jus cogens norms of international law, and international conventions. Relentless ethnic cleansing through killings, intimidation, hate speech and the denial of the right of return has led to endless human suffering, fragmented communities and deep injustices. Certainly, guaranteeing the right of return must be at the center of international efforts to restore justice, achieve peace and reconciliation.

Giving an international legal value to the ethnic cleansing, terrorism, aggression, genocide, war and crimes against humanity committed by the Armenian state against our people and remaining unpunished, helping Azerbaijanis whose human rights and freedoms have been violated in international legal documents to

return safely and with dignity to their homes, ethnic cleansing, violence and the destruction of Azerbaijani heritage, and those who obstructed the return of forcibly displaced Azerbaijanis should be brought before international courts and punished, and the Armenian state should be forced to pay material and moral compensation.

References

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